

Growth Performance of Three Nigerian Chickens Reared in a Humid Tropical Environment

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Received: December 17, 2023; Accepted: May 23, 2024; Published: May 26, 2024.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11303884

Abstract: The study was conducted to determine the growth performance of three Nigerian chicken breeds (The Three Nigerian Breeds). A total of one hundred and fifty (150) day old birds were used for this purpose which comprising of fifty (50) birds each of the Noiler, naked neck and the normal feather chickens were used in a completely randomized design. The birds were raised on deep litter from day old to sixteenth week of age during which data were collected on the body weight, linear body measurement and the performance index. Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance using SPSS software package. Results obtained showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) on the performance index and all linear body parameters measured. The Naked neck showed better feed conversion ratio (2.11 ± 0.088) compared to the other breeds. Noiler recorded the best performance in all the measured traits. The better performance of Noiler over the other two breeds could be attributed to its genetic make-up which could be linked to the development of the breed.

Keywords: Nigerian chicken, breed, bodyweight, linear measurements.

Introduction

The ever-increasing population of the world and the need for balanced meal especially protein diets have made it most essential to satisfy humans food requirements (Liu *et al.*, 2011). Chicken meat consumption has proven to be the most prevalent alternative towards bridging the gap for animal protein deficiency in human diets (Obasoyo *et al.*, 2005).

Poultry sub-sector creates employment and promotes overall economic development (King' Ori *et al.*, 2010), while local chicken production contributes to the income and general wellbeing of the rural dwellers (Sonaiya, 2007).

Many of the features related to the functions of chickens have been substantially improved by the genetic selection through crossing the different varieties to meet the increasing

global need for chicken meat (Rekaya *et al.*, 2013). As a result of genetic improvement over the years, the Nigerian native chickens have been improved. Thus, the main purpose of animal breeding practices is to improve traits of economic importance (Yunusa and Adeoti, 2014).

Growth performance of an animal is a phenotypic expression which is the outward expression of the animal genetic make-up (Ojedapo *et al.*, 2012). Growth in animals involves increase in body size and changes in functional capabilities of the various tissues and organs of the body (Akpan *et al.*, 2022). Recent studies have shown that other growth traits such as body length, shank length and breast girth can serve as good indicators of growth other than body weight (Ige, 2013). The live body weight of an animal is an important variable that determines the market value of an animal (Kadurumba *et al.*, 2023).

Materials and Methods

Experimental location

The study was conducted at the Poultry Unit of Teaching and Research Farms, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Ohaji-Egbema, Imo State. Ohaji Egbema situates in the humid tropics at latitude 5^o15'N and longitude 6^o58'E with a total mean annual rainfall of about 2,500mm

and average temperature of 26^oC (NIMET, 2014).

Experimental bird

One hundred and fifty birds were used for the purpose of this study comprising of 50 Noiler, 50 Naked neck and 50 Normal feather chickens. The birds were raised from day old to sixteen weeks of age during which data were collected.

Management of experimental birds

The birds were brooded and raised on a deep litter pen. Feeds and water were provided *ad libitum* throughout the experiment. Daily management operations such as washing of the feeders and drinkers were carried out daily and litters were changed as at when due. Vaccination and medication schedule were strictly adhered to and bio-safety was also ensured.

Experimental design and statistical model

The birds were housed on three deep litter pens according to their breed. The experimental design used was Completely Randomized (CRD), thus the model:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \beta_i + \sum_{ij}$$

Where

Y_{ij} = Observation on the jth individual
bird of the ith breed

μ = the overall mean

B_i = breed effect

ϵ_{ij} = Random residual effect

Data collection

Data were collected on Growth and Performance index from day old to the sixteenth week of the experiment as follows:

Body weight (g)

The birds were weighed individually at the beginning of the experiment and subsequently every week from day old to 16th week of age, every week using electronic digital scale (Camry ISO 9001 model EK5350).

Feed Intake (g)

Quantity of feed consumed was determined by subtracting the quantity left over the next morning from the quantity offered.

Average weight gain

This was calculated as:

$$\text{Weight gain} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{NoD}}$$

Where

W_1 = the Initial weight

W_2 = the final weight

NoD = Number of days

Feed conversion ratio: $\frac{\text{Feed Intake}}{\text{Weight gain}}$

Linear measurements

Body Length (cm)

This was taken as the distance between the last cervical vertebra and the caudal vertebra. It was done with the use of a measuring tape.

Breast girth (cm)

This was taken as the circumference of the chest around the deepest region.

Shank length (cm)

It was taken as the length of the tarso-metatarsus from the anterior end joining the tibia bone to the first digit.

Drumstick length (cm)

This was measured as the distance between the patella and the posterior end of the tibia joining the tarso metatarsus.

Drumstick girth

This was taken as the circumference at the biggest region of the drumstick.

Height at withers (cm)

This was measured on the dorsal midline at the highest point on the withers.

Shoulder to tail length

This was taken as the distance from the point of the shoulder to pin bone or to the end of occygeal vertebrate.

Wing length (cm)

The length of the wing from the end of the wing to the bone that attaches the wing to the body.

Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the General Linear Model procedure of SPSS (2014). Means were separated using the Duncan Multiple Range Test as outlined in the software package (SPSS 2014).

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presented the growth performance index of the Noiler, the Naked neck and the Normal feather. The result is presented in form of means from general linear model for initial and final body weights respectively, weight gains, initial feed intake and final feed intake, average feed intake, daily feed intake and feed conversion ratio. Noiler recorded significant ($p < 0.05$) higher initial body weight than the other two breeds. Non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in the final body weight and weight gain of the three breeds.

For the feed intake, non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference was observed in the initial feed

intake between the Noiler and the naked neck while significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the final feed intake, mean feed intake and daily feed intake amongst the three breeds of chicken studied. Significant ($p < 0.05$) feed conversion ratio was recorded between the naked neck and the other two breeds. The result showed that the Naked neck has better feed conversion ratio (2.11 ± 0.088) than the other two breeds. This is followed by Normal feather chicken with feed conversion ratio of 3.06 ± 0.156 . Ajayi (2010) reported that naked neck genes confer better feed conversion, growth rate and feed efficiency compared to the normal feathered chicken. The naked neck gene (Na) and its effect on heat dissipation positively increases feed intake resulting in higher body weight under high temperatures (Islam and Nishibori, 2009). N'Dri *et al.* (2006) reported the feed conversion ratio of 3.15 in slow growing line of chicken which is close to the values obtained in this study. Ogbu *et al* (2013) reported the feed conversion ratio of 4.69 and 5.17 for light ecotype and heavy ecotype chickens respectively.

Table 1 Growth performance index of three Nigerian chicken breeds from 0-16 weeks of age

Performance index	Noiler	Naked neck	Normal feather
Initial body weight (kg)	0.035 ± 0.00 ^a	0.0312 ± 0.00 ^b	0.0299 ± 0.00 ^b
Final body weight (kg)	2.02 ± 0.105	1.99 ± 0.065	1.72 ± 0.082
Weight gain (kg)	1.99 ± 0.105	1.96 ± 0.065	1.69 ± 0.082
Initial feed intake (kg)	0.71 ± 0.000 ^a	0.67 ± 0.000 ^a	0.58 ± 0.000 ^b
Final feed intake (kg)	6.07 ± 0.028 ^a	3.99 ± 0.055 ^c	4.84 ± 0.061 ^b
Mean feed intake (kg)	5.24 ± 0.020 ^a	3.21 ± 0.062 ^c	4.23 ± 0.075 ^b
Daily feed intake (kg)	0.05 ± 0.000 ^a	0.03 ± 0.001 ^c	0.04 ± 0.001 ^b
Feed conversion ratio (FCR)	3.30 ± 0.166 ^a	2.11 ± 0.088 ^b	3.06 ± 0.156 ^a

Means within rows with different superscript are significantly difference (P<0.05)

Result on linear measurement is presented in Table 2. Significant difference ($p<0.05$) was observed in all the parameters (body weight, body length, breast girth, shank length, drumstick length and girth, shoulder to tail length, height at withers and wing length) measured among the three breeds.

Noiler recorded the best performance in all the measured traits similarly, followed by the Naked neck breed which outperformed the normal feather in all the measured traits. The better performance of Noiler over the other two breeds could be attributed to its genetic make-up which could be linked to the development of the breed, since Noiler is a cross between broilers and cockerels; hence they develop meat like broiler chicken. Yakubu *et al.* (2008) reported that naked neck birds perform better in terms of body weight

than normal feathered birds. The Naked neck gene (Na) was reported to increase breast yield meat while its advantage over normal feathered conditions were found to be exhibited during egg production (Adebambo, 2015). Okafor (2019) reported the body length range of 23.00±0.31 to 26.31 ± 0.38cm, the shank length range of 10.12 to 11.94cm and breast girth range of 21.46 to 27.15cm which were within the ranges obtained in this study.

Table 2 Linear measurement of three Nigerian chicken breeds from 0-16 weeks of age

Linear measurement	Noiler	Naked neck	Normal feather
Body weight (kg)	1.150 ± 0.020 ^a	1.039 ± 0.020 ^b	0.909 ± 0.020 ^c
Body length (cm)	33.37 ± 0.127 ^a	32.16 ± 0.127 ^b	31.46 ± 0.127 ^c
Breast length (cm)	21.66 ± 0.119 ^a	20.95 ± 0.119 ^b	19.78 ± 0.117 ^c
Shank length (cm)	10.03 ± 0.053 ^a	9.77 ± 0.058 ^b	9.43 ± 0.058 ^c
Drumstick length (cm)	12.99 ± 0.131 ^a	12.34 ± 0.131 ^b	12.09 ± 0.131 ^c
Drumstick girth (cm)	9.76 ± 0.084 ^a	9.52 ± 0.034 ^b	9.14 ± 0.084 ^c
Shoulder to tail length (cm)	17.53 ± 0.085 ^a	17.00 ± 0.085 ^b	16.76 ± 0.085 ^c
Height at withers (cm)	22.29 ± 0.095 ^a	21.97 ± 0.095 ^b	20.50 ± 0.095 ^c
Wing length	18.47 ± 0.078 ^a	17.92 ± 0.078 ^b	17.67 ± 0.078 ^c

^{abc}Means within rows with different superscript are significantly difference ($P>0.05$)

Conclusion

The study concluded that although Noiler chicken showed poor feed conversion ratio, it had the best performance compared to the other breeds which could be attributed to its genetic make-up since it is a cross between broilers and cockerels.

Acknowledgement

This work is part of a wider study funded by Institution Based Research (IBR) with Grant number: TETF/DR&D/CE/UNI/UMUAGWO/IBR/2022/VOL.1/#26.

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